

pyroomacoustics

Eric Bezzam, PhD Student at EPFL

Self-introduction (Eric Bezzam)

currently

PhD Student @ EPFL in Switzerland (Prof. Martin Vetterli)

previously

Speech recognition and signal processing
@ Snips/Sonos (Paris, '18-20')
and DSP Concepts (California, '17)

research

- Computational imaging (lensless, ultrasound)
- Multi-microphone processing (DoA, beamforming)
- Open-source and reproducibility

hobbies

Soccer, American lit/history, Organizing tech events (LauzHack)

github

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EPFL

SONOS

LauzHack

Outline

1. Pyroomacoustics Overview and Main Features
2. Origin, Technical Evolution, Learnings
3. Pyroomacoustics in Research / Industry

Overview and Main Features

Motivation (typical audio DSP dev cycle...)

Data generation / augmentation

Without pyroomacoustics: few RIR examples and difficult to collect → **limited**

With pyroomacoustics: easy to generate multi-microphone data → **diverse and convenient**

Prototyping of DSP algorithms

Without pyroomacoustics: implement from scratch and and set up experiment → **time consuming**

With pyroomacoustics: simulation and reference algorithms → **fast and short cycle**

Package summary

- Content**
- Room acoustics simulator (Python API, C++ backend).
 - Single- and multi-channel audio processing algorithms.

Install

```
$ pip install pyroomacoustics
```

Python

3.8, 3.9, 3.10, 3.11, 3.12

Requires

numpy, scipy, Cython, pybind11,

Optional

matplotlib, sounddevice, samplerate, mir_eval

Docs

pyroomacoustics.readthedocs.io

GitHub

github.com/LCAV/pyroomacoustics (1.4 ★, 422 🙌)

Modular package

Plenty of example scripts:

<https://github.com/LCAV/pyroomacoustics/tree/master/examples>

Simulation of sound propagation

Described by wave equation:

$$\Delta^2 p(\mathbf{r}, t) = \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial t^2}$$

Precise simulation → Finite element methods, e.g. with COMSOL (*expensive*)

Approximate with **image source method** (ISM) [1].

Point source in free space:

$$p(\mathbf{r}, t) = \frac{1}{r} \left(\text{Attenuation} \right) \left(\text{Delay} \right)$$

Image source method (ISM) example

1. Place microphone(s)
and source(s)

Image source method (ISM) example

2. Mirror sources across walls → **images**

Mirror images across walls for **multiple reflections**

Image source method (ISM) example

3. Sum point source contributions of all sources

$$u_{\text{Arlt}}(t) \equiv \sum_i$$

Image source method (ISM) example

3. Sum point source contributions of all sources

$$u(\mathbf{r}, t) \equiv \sum_i$$

pyroomacoustics implementation

Code example


```
import numpy as np
import pyroomacoustics as pra

room = pra.ShoeBox([10, 5, 3.2], fs=16000, absorption=0.25, max_order=17)

# add one source at a time, optionally pass source signal
room.add_source([2.5, 1.7, 1.69], signal=my_signal)

# add microphone array, R.shape == (3, n_mics)
R = np.array([[5.71, 2.31, 1.4], [5.72, 2.32, 1.4]]).T
room.add_microphone_array(pra.MicrophoneArray(R, fs=room.fs))

room.simulate()
output_signal = room.mic_array.signals # (n_mics, n_samples)

room.plot(img_order=3) # show room
room.plot_rir() # show RIR
```

Additional Simulation Options

Ray Tracing (RT)

To account for scattering [1].

[1] Schröder (2011), *Physically Based Real-Time Auralization of Interactive Virtual Environments*.

Hybrid (ISM + RT)

Cyril


```
# Create the room
room = pra.Shoebox(
    room_dim,
    fs=16000,
    max_order=3,
    ray_tracing=True,
)

# Activate the ray tracing
room.set_ray_tracing()
```

Frequency-Dependent Coefficients

From [database](#) of materials [1].

Absorption Coefficients

Massive constructions and hard surfaces

keyword	description	125 Hz	250 Hz	500 Hz	1 kHz	2 kHz	4 kHz	8 kHz
hard_surface	Walls, hard surfaces average (brick walls, plaster, hard floors, etc.)	0.02	0.02	0.03	0.03	0.04	0.05	0.05
brickwork	Walls, rendered brickwork	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.03	0.03	0.04	0.04
rough_concrete	Rough concrete	0.02	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.04	0.07	0.07
	Smooth un-							

```
import pyroomacoustics as pra

m = pra.make_materials(
    ceiling="hard_surface",
    floor="6mm_carpet",
    east="brickwork",
    west="brickwork",
    north="brickwork",
    south="brickwork",
)

room = pra.ShoeBox(
    [9, 7.5, 3.5], fs=16000,
    materials=m, max_order=3,
    air_absorption=True,
    ray_tracing=True
)
```

[1] Vorlaender, *Auralization*, 1st ed. Berlin: Springer-Verlag, 2008, pp. 1-340.

Microphone and Source Directivities

Satvik


```
# create directivity object
from pyroomacoustics.directivities import (
    DirectivityPattern, DirectionVector,
    CardioidFamily,
)

dir_obj = CardioidFamily(
    orientation=DirectionVector(
        azimuth=90, colatitude=15, degrees=True
    ),
    pattern_enum=DirectivityPattern.HYPERCARDIOID
)

# place the source in the room
room.add_source(
    position=[2.5, 3.73, 1.76], directivity=dir_obj
)

# place microphone array in the room
room.add_microphone_array(
    mic_locs, directivity=[dir_1, dir_2]
)
```

Demo notebook ([GitHub](#))

pyroomacoustics demo

In this IPython notebook, we demonstrate a few features of `pyroomacoustics` :

1. Its *pythonic* and convenient object-oriented interface.
2. The Room Impulse Response (RIR) generator.
3. Provided reference algorithms.

Below is a list of the examples (run all cells as some may depend on previous imports and results).

1. Creating a 2D/3D room
2. Adding sources and microphones
3. Room Impulse Response generation and propagation simulation
4. Beamforming
5. Direction-of-arrival
6. Adaptive filtering
7. STFT processing
8. Source Separation

Simulation outputs

Dry sound

ISM17

ISM3 + RT
(scattering)

ISM3 + RT
(scattering, air abs)

Bedroom (small)

Office (medium)

Hall (large)

Origin, Technical Evolution, Learnings

Origin (Aug 2014)

Robin

LCAV at EPFL needs RIR simulator for *beamforming* research.

Current RIR simulators: in-house / MatLab ([AudioLabs at FAU](#), [Roomsim](#)).

People gradually switching to Python.

Pyroomacoustics open-sourced (Dec 24, 2015).

Release of Amazon Alexa (Nov 2014).

Other Python packages: [gpuRIR](#) (2018), [Pygsound](#) (2019), [FAST-RIR](#) (2021)

Technical evolution

(2015) Python library for simulating RIRs with ISM + algorithms (adaptive filtering, beamforming, source separation).

(2018) **C extension** for efficiently building RIR (Cython).

(2020) **C++ extension** for ray tracing support with [eigen](#) and [pybind11](#).

(2024) Fully replaced C with C++.

pybind11

Research and student projects continuously contributed to simulator and algorithms!

Learnings from *pyroomacoustics*

Open-sourcing is extremely valuable (for community and personal development).

Whether your project takes off...

doesn't matter as above reasons are already great 🙌

depends on **trends**, **continuous development/support**, **accessibility**.

Accessibility: easy-to-install (Python), documentation, clear examples/API.

Interested in open-source Python project?

pydevtips.readthedocs.io

python-dev-tips

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.github/workflows

Fix branch to PR.

last year

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docs passing

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Research with Pyroomacoustics

Research with *pyroomacoustics*

Enabled our research: [beamforming](#) (2015), [direction-of-arrival](#) (2017), [source separation](#) (2019), [keyword spotting](#) (2020).

Main usage in **data generation/augmentation** for speech applications.

Out of 553 citations ([Google Scholar](#)):

- Speech recognition (420)
- Separation (379)
- Localization (268)
- Speech enhancement (351)
- Multichannel (258)
- Adaptive filtering (237)
- Dereverberation (172)
- Denoising (144)

Pyroomacoustics in Industry

SONOS

 TorchAudio

Sonos Voice Control (SVC)

[1] <https://tech-blog.sonos.com/posts/reproducing-on-device-data-accurately-for-private-by-design-voice-control/>

[2] Eric Bezzam, Robin Scheibler, Cyril Cadoux, and Thibault Gisselbrecht (2020). "A study on more realistic room simulation for far-field keyword spotting".

Image Source Method ([link](#))

TORCHAUDIO.PROTOTYPE.FUNCTIONAL.SIMULATE_RIR_ISM

```
torchaudio.prototype.functional.simulate_rir_ism(  
    room: Tensor,  
    source: Tensor,  
    mic_array: Tensor,  
    max_order: int,  
    absorption: Union[float, Tensor],  
    output_length: Optional[int] = None,  
    delay_filter_length: int = 81,  
    center_frequency: Optional[Tensor] = None,  
    sound_speed: float = 343.0,  
    sample_rate: float = 16000.0  
) → Tensor [SOURCE]
```

Compute Room Impulse Response (RIR) based on the *image source method* [Allen and Berkley, 1979]. The implementation is based on *pyroomacoustics* [Scheibler et al., 2018].

Ray Tracing ([link](#))

TORCHAUDIO.PROTOTYPE.FUNCTIONAL.RAY_TRACING

```
torchaudio.prototype.functional.ray_tracing(  
    room: Tensor,  
    source: Tensor,  
    mic_array: Tensor,  
    num_rays: int,  
    absorption: Union[float, Tensor] = 0.0,  
    scattering: Union[float, Tensor] = 0.0,  
    mic_radius: float = 0.5,  
    sound_speed: float = 343.0,  
    energy_thres: float = 1e-07,  
    time_thres: float = 10.0,  
    hist_bin_size: float = 0.004  
) → Tensor [SOURCE]
```

Compute energy histogram via ray tracing.

The implementation is based on *pyroomacoustics* [Scheibler et al., 2018].

Designing your recording studio

The screenshot shows a YouTube video player with a code editor overlay. The code editor displays a plot of a signal and a section titled "Define Materials".

Define Materials

The materials used for the wall floor and ceiling will define the absorption, reflection, and scattering of sound. You have three options for defining the absorption properties of the materials.

1. The most basic case is to enter a single absorption coefficient like `pra.Material(energy_absorption=0.6, scattering=0.4)`
2. Browse for real materials in the pyroomacoustics materials database (with frequency dependent absorption) which can be entered like: `pra.Material('rockwool_50mm_80kgm3')`
3. You can make your own frequency dependent absorption materials like: `pra.Material(energy_absorption=[0.4, 0.8, 0.99], 'center_freqs': [100, 250, 500, 1000, 10000], scattering=0.4)`

Note: I have noticed a bug in the frequency dependent attenuation - best to stick to single absorption coefficients.

The video player shows the video title "Setting up your room" and the channel "Astrobear Music" with 1.77K subscribers. The video has 48 likes and includes options for share, clip, and save.

Conclusion

- Simulation of *room acoustics* (ISM, ray tracing, hybrid, air absorption, frequency-dependent materials, directivities).
- Reference implementations of *single- and multi-channel processing*.
- Enables *prototyping* for ASR and experimenting algorithms/setups.

What's next?

- Directivities: incorporating measured, and ray tracing.
- Moving sources.
- **Help is very welcome!** <https://github.com/LCAV/pyroomacoustics>

Collaborators

Robin

Cyril

Juan

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Prerak

Thank you!

Lab mates

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Used by 241

Contributors 26

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